

1 The influence of three common antibiotics on coastal benthic foraminifera: 2 implications for culture experiments and biomonitoring

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11

12 Abstract

13 Synthetic antibiotics are medicinal substances crucial for human and animal health and
14 welfare. Recently they are expansively used in food industry for e.g. reducing bacterial
15 infections in livestock, poultry, and aquaculture. Due to their extensive use, antibiotics are
16 increasingly accumulating in coastal marine ecosystems and cause damage to marine
17 organisms. In this study we investigated the influence of antibiotics on benthic foraminifera,
18 which are widespread marine protists. Foraminifera are often used as bioindicators to define
19 the health state of coastal ecosystems. To gain deeper insights into the ecology of foraminifera
20 and enhance their use as bioindicators, numerous studies have conducted laboratory
21 experiments, some of which employing antibiotics to prevent bacterial infections in the
22 cultures. However, for decades it remained unresolved whether antibiotics have either a
23 negative or positive effect on foraminifera. In this study we tested the influence of three
24 commonly used antibiotics (ampicillin, chloramphenicol, and tetracycline) as well as a mixture
25 of the three on nutrient uptake of two benthic foraminifera, temperate fjord species
26 *Nonionella* sp. T1 and large tropical species *Heterostegina depressa*. Our results showed that
27 tetracycline present alone or in mixture has the most negative influence on the nutrition
28 uptake of foraminifera, and under light conditions may completely inactivate foraminiferal
29 activity. Ampicillin showed a less negative impact likely caused by a hydrolysis of this drug in
30 seawater over days. Finally, chloramphenicol reduced the nutrient uptake of the symbiont-
31 bearing *H. depressa* but not that of *Nonionella* sp. T1, which indicates that this antibiotic exerts
32 a species-specific effect. However, given that the applied herein antibiotic concentrations were
33 high following the supplier's recommendation for laboratory cultures, an extrapolation of
34 these results to antibiotic concentrations occurring in coastal waters is difficult.

35

36 1. Introduction

37 1.1. Antibiotics as pollutants in aquatic microenvironments

38 Antibiotics are bioactive chemical compounds, which act against bacteria by either killing them
39 (bactericidal antibiotics) or by inhibiting their growth (bacteriostatic antibiotics). Nowadays,
40 antibiotics are extensively used in both human and veterinary medicine, both causing their
41 release with sewer outlets and subsequent accumulation in the environment. Other areas of
42 antibiotics application such as agriculture, livestock and aquaculture cause direct introduction
43 of antibiotics into terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Antibiotics can enter the hydrosphere
44 both as unaltered parent compounds and as antibiotic metabolites (Gothwal and Shashidhar,
45 2015). In fact, between 50-80% of the ingested antibiotics are excreted by organisms unaltered
46 and enter the environment through faeces and urine (Lienert et al., 2007). As a result,
47 antibiotics reach the sea indirectly via rivers and groundwater from agricultural and urban
48 point sources (Garcia-Galan et al., 2010) or are directly introduced in aquaculture (Adenaya et
49 al., 2023). Concentrations of antibiotics in groundwater can range from few ng L⁻¹ to several
50 µg L⁻¹ (Gros et al., 2021). For instance, China is the world's largest producer and consumer of
51 antibiotics (Zhang et al., 2015), with around 2.5 x 10⁴ tons of antibiotics being consumed
52 annually (Bu et al., 2013), which causes a strong accumulation of antibiotics in the Chinese
53 coastal zones (Wang et al., 2023). The negative influence of antibiotics in seawater has been
54 studied for several marine organisms. For instance, the water flea *Daphnia magna* sensitively
55 reacts to the presence of antibiotics and shows increased mortality at increased
56 concentrations (Bawa-Allah and Ehimiyein 2022). Further, antibiotics have negative side effects
57 like ototoxicity, nephrotoxicity or tendinopathy in mammalian cells (Khaliq et al., 2003) and
58 can lead to dysfunction and oxidative damage in eukaryotic cells (Kalghatgi et al., 2013).
59 Further, antibiotics can accumulate in organisms (bioaccumulation) and transferred via food
60 chain (Hu et al., 2023). In summary, the presence of antibiotics in surface water, groundwater
61 and seawater causes exposure of (micro)biota to these pollutants, either directly or through
62 trophic interactions and feeding activities, as antibiotics can also accumulate in plants and thus
63 find their way into the food chain of higher organisms (Gothwal and Shashidhar, 2015).

64

65 1.2. Foraminifera and antibiotics

66 Foraminifera are marine protists found in all marine habitats in high abundance. In the late
67 1960s it was suggested that the presence of bacteria in the culture medium affect the growth
68 of foraminifera under laboratory conditions (Müller and Lee, 1969). First attempts of removing
69 bacteria as ectobionts from foraminifera by antibiotics treatment resulted in failed growth of
70 foraminifera (e.g. Lee and Pierce, 1963), whilst later studies demonstrated that streptomycin
71 increases growth of foraminifera (Nigram et al., 1996). Yet, Nigram et al. (1996) only tested the
72 impact of one antibiotic type on the growth of foraminifera but did not investigate potential
73 effects on their nutritional and metabolic activity. Interestingly, the study of Nigram et al.
74 (1996) remains relevant as - due to the initial widespread use of streptomycin in medicine -
75 many bacterial species have evolved or acquired streptomycin resistance (e.g., Cohen et al.,
76 2020). Some studies also tried to address how mixtures of different antibiotics affect
77 foraminifera under laboratory conditions. For instance, a mixture of streptomycin, penicillin
78 and amphotericin B was shown to inhibit the growth of multiple foraminifera (Lee et al., 1991),
79 whilst chloramphenicol and streptomycin (Arnold, 1966) or chloramphenicol,
80 dihydrostreptomycin, neomycin, penicillin and tetracycline (Pierce, 1965) did not inhibit

81 growth and reproduction across several foraminiferal species. The latter approach was
82 adopted by experiments addressing denitrification in benthic foraminifera and requiring
83 bacteria-free cultures (e.g. Bernhard et al., 2012). Nowadays many studies on foraminifera are
84 carried out using antibiotics though the impact of antibiotics on the nutritional and metabolic
85 activity of the foraminifera has barely been studied.

86 At present, a variety of different antibiotics is in use, which have different mechanisms of
87 action and therefore also affect different bacteria. In this study we investigated the effects of
88 three antibiotics commonly used in human and animal treatment, which are also frequently
89 used in cell cultures. Those include (1) ampicillin (AMP), (2) chloramphenicol (CAM) and (3)
90 tetracycline (TET).

91 (1) **Ampicillin** is classified as a beta-lactam, which consists of a highly reactive ring made up of
92 three carbon and one nitrogen atom. Through the interaction of this ring with proteins of the
93 bacterial cell wall, the synthesis of the cell wall is disrupted and the growth of the bacteria is
94 inhibited (Etebu and Ariekpar, 2016). Under light protection AMP is degrading slowly
95 following a temperature dependent pattern, e.g., within 24 hours 6% of AMP degrades at 4 °C
96 and 10% at 23 °C (Zhang and Trissel, 2002). AMP degradation is also pH sensitive, with half-life
97 times decreasing from 31 days to 27 and 7 days when pH increased from 4 to 7 and 9,
98 respectively (Mitchell et al., 2014).

99 (2) **Chloramphenicol** is a 50S ribosome inhibitor and physically block the initiation phase of
100 protein translation in bacteria (Patel and Bonomo, 2011). CAM has a low water solubility (2.5-
101 4.4 mg/ml at 25 °C) and decomposed rapidly through hydrolysis at pH < 9.5 (Shaw, 1975). The
102 CAM molecule is relatively temperature insensitive with only 50% of CAM being inactivated at
103 37 °C during six months (Shaw, 1975).

104 (3) **Tetracycline** disrupts the protein synthesis in bacteria by preventing the elongation of poly
105 peptide chains through curtailing the amino acid addition (Etebu and Ariekpar, 2016). With
106 10 mg/ml the water solubility is intermediate and comparable with CAM (Ali, 1984). TET
107 quickly degrades in acidic solutions in the pH range 2 to 7, whilst above pH=7, TET is relatively
108 stable (Ali, 1984). However, the biggest challenge with this antibiotic is its sensitivity to visible
109 light. After 2 hours of light exposure, 27% of the initial amount of tetracycline is degraded
110 (Oluwole and Olatunji, 2022).

111 In our study we investigate the influence of the antibiotics AMP, CAM and TET as well as their
112 mixture (MIX) on the nutrition of foraminifera. We studied two benthic foraminiferal species
113 from two different habitats. *Heterostegina depressa* d'Orbigny, a large shallow-water tropical
114 benthic foraminifer with algal endosymbionts, was herein incubated in light conditions and at
115 25°C. *Nonionella* sp. T1, on the other hand, is a temperate species, which was incubated in the
116 dark conditions and at 10°C because it comes from a ~40-m deep fjord setting. Through this
117 combination, sensitivity of antibiotics to both light and temperature was investigated in this
118 study.

119

120 **2. Material and Methods**

121 2.1. Sediment sampling and sampling area

122 Sediment sampling in the Gullmar Fjord for living *Nonionella* sp. T1 was performed on 2nd of
123 October 2023 aboard of R/V Alice (University of Gothenburg) by using a box corer at Station 3
124 in the outer part of the Gullmar Fjord (58°15.538'N, 11°27.483'E and 40 m water depth: Fig.
125 1).

126 Gullmar Fjord is located on the west coast of Sweden, with a maximum water depth of 118.6
127 m. It is one of the most well-studied marine settings in the world with the first hydrographic
128 observations taken as early as 1869 (Ekman, 1870). Being a sill fjord, Gullmar Fjord has
129 remarkably high sediment accumulation rates of 0,7-1.4 cm yr⁻¹ (Filipsson and Nordberg, 2004)
130 and low tidal activity providing a high-resolution paleo-environmental archive (e.g. Harland et
131 al., 2013; Polovodova Asteman et al, 2018). Due to its high biodiversity, Gullmar Fjord has
132 become the first marine conservation area in Sweden in 1983 and has currently no
133 anthropogenic impact.

134

135

136 Figure 1: Map showing the location of the study area (Gullmar Fjord) and the sampling site (star).

137

138 In parallel to the sediment sampling, environmental data (temperature, salinity, and oxygen)
139 were taken on board by using a CTD probe. The T, S and O₂ observations proximal to the sea
140 floor showed 14.9°C, salinity of 33 and 4.1 ml O₂ l⁻¹, respectively. The retrieved sediment
141 surface in the box corer was intact and covered by water, which was gently siphoned out by
142 using a plastic tube. The upper 5 cm of the sediment were transferred to a bucket and taken
143 to the lab at Kristineberg Centre for Marine Research and Innovation. There the sediment was
144 gently sieved by using a 63 and 1000 µm sieves and ambient fjord water to concentrate living
145 foraminifera and remove larger meiofauna. The resulting sediment fraction (63-1000 µm) with

146 living *Nonionella* sp. T1 was collected in wide-neck PVC bottles and sent to the Institute of
147 Geological Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences (ING PAN), Krakow for experimental work.

148 Sediments containing the large benthic foraminifera *Heterostegina depressa* come from a main
149 culture, hosted at the Department of Palaeontology of the University of Vienna for many years,
150 which originally come from a shark tank in the “Haus der Natur” located in the city of Salzburg
151 (Austria). In Vienna, *H. depressa* is continuously cultivated at a temperature of 25°C, a salinity
152 of 35 PSU, and light intensity at 40 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in an 8h-16h light/dark rhythm. The
153 sediment with living *H. depressa* was sent to the ING PAN Research Center in Kraków to run
154 the experiments in the Biogeosystem Modelling Lab (BioGeoLab).

155

156 2.2. Experimental Setup

157 All cultivation experiments were carried out at the ING PAN BioGeoLab in Kraków. After the
158 sediment arrived from the different sampling locations, two separate main cultures were
159 created. For that, the sediment was placed in glass aquaria and covered with artificial seawater
160 (salinity of 33 for Gullmar Fjord and 35 for Vienna sediments). In alignment with the lifestyles
161 of the two selected species, the aquarium containing the Gullmar Fjord sediment was placed
162 in the dark at 15°C, whilst the Vienna sediment was placed at room temperature (25°C) and
163 was illuminated with an 8:16 hour light cycle. After a week-long acclimatization phase, the
164 sediment was washed over a 150 μm sieve and living foraminifera, which had a characteristic
165 brown-yellow color of the cytoplasm, were removed using a fine brush. *Nonionella* sp. T1 was
166 collected from the Gullmar Fjord sediments and *H. depressa* from the Vienna culture.
167 Following that, all foraminifera were cleaned with a brush and all adhering particles were
168 carefully removed and transferred to a crystallization dish, placed in the center of the dish, and
169 left for one day to test their vitality by a so called “crawling test”. For this purpose, the
170 foraminifera are placed centrally in a petri dish. After a few hours, those foraminifera that have
171 moved away from the center and thus showed pseudopodia activity were used for the
172 experiments. After one day, only the actively moving individuals were selected for further
173 feeding experiments.

174 For feeding and isotopic uptake experiments, 15 individuals of *Nonionella* sp. T1, and one
175 individual for *H. depressa* were placed per separate crystallization dish and covered with
176 100 ml artificial seawater water with a salinity similar to that observed at the sampling sites. .
177 The cultures without antibiotics served as control samples. The experiments with *Nonionella*
178 sp. T1 were performed in triplicates, whilst for *H. depressa* 6 replicates were used. Different
179 replication was done in order to get a final mass of 1 mg dry weight of cytoplasm for further
180 analysis. As interference factor three antibiotics (Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol and Tetracycline)
181 were used in two concentrations and additionally as a mixture containing all three antibiotics
182 together. The low concentration (c1) was based on the recommendation from the providing
183 company (Roth) to keep culture medium free of bacterial activity. Therefore, we created 4
184 culture media on c1 level separately enriched with 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ AMP (Ampicillin), 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ CAM
185 (Chloramphenicol), 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ TET (Tetracycline) and a mixture (MIX) of 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ AMP, 50
186 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ CAM and 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ TET altogether. To see an effect of the increasing concentration we

187 created further 4 culture media (c2) with ten times higher levels of antibiotics: 300 µg/ml AMP,
188 500 µg/ml CAM, 1000 µg/ml TET and a MIX of the same respective concentrations.

189 To observe the change in the metabolic activity of the foraminifera, lyophilized isotopic
190 labelled alga powder (*Chaetoceros simplex* var. *calcitrans*) was added to the cultures with
191 *Nonionella* sp. T1. This diatom species also occurs naturally in the Gullmar Fjord (Hallfors,
192 2004). *Chaetoceros simplex* var. *calcitrans* was grown in a nutrient medium enriched with ¹³C
193 and ¹⁵N and therefore contains an increased concentration of isotopes (for method details see
194 Lintner et al., 2020). Since *H. depressa* with its symbionts is fully autotrophic (Röttger et al.,
195 1980), we directly spiked the culture medium containing these foraminifera with NaH¹³CO₃
196 (0.2 mM) and Na¹⁵NO₃ (0.2mM) to investigate the isotopic uptake. Following this, the
197 experimental setups for both species were incubated with antibiotics for three and seven days.

198

199 2.3. Sample and data processing

200 After incubation with the isotopic enriched algae, *Nonionella* sp. T1 individuals were removed
201 from the culture and cleaned of any adhering particles using a brush. To measure the isotopic
202 uptake, 15 specimens of *Nonionella* sp. T1 and 1 specimen of *H. depressa* were transferred to
203 separate Sn-capsules. In total, 48 capsules for *Nonionella* sp. T1 (4 antibiotics x 2
204 concentrations x 2-time points x 3 replicates) and 96 capsules for *H. depressa* (4 antibiotics x 2
205 concentrations x 2-time points x six replicates) were used. Afterwards, the capsules including
206 foraminifera were dried for 3 days at room temperature. The calcitic test was then removed
207 by adding 12 µl 4% hydrochloric acid (HCl) to each capsule. Finally, the capsules were dried at
208 50°C for three days and sent to the University of Vienna for further measurements. The isotope
209 mass ratio was measured at the Stable Isotope Laboratory for Environmental Research (SILVER
210 – University of Vienna; IRMS, Delta^{PLUS}, coupled by a ConFlo III interface to an elemental
211 analyzer EA 1110, Thermo Finnigan was used to measure ratios of ¹³C/¹²C and ¹⁵N/¹⁴N by using
212 Vienna PeeDee Belemnite Standard R_{VPDB} = 0.0112372 for C and atmospheric nitrogen R_{atmN} =
213 0.0036765 for N), and the calculation of the amount of phytodetrital isotopes (pC and pN) for
214 *Nonionella* sp. T1 versus incorporated isotopes (IC and IN) for *H. depressa* was done according
215 to Lintner et al. (2020). To investigate the influence of antibiotics on the metabolism of
216 foraminifera, the pC:pN (IC:IN) ratio is calculated to determine whether the foraminifera are
217 in a stressed state or not (Lintner et al., 2025). Two-way analysis of variance tests (ANOVA)
218 (level of significance p = 0.05) using PAST4.0 software (Hammer et al., 2001) were performed
219 to test, whether the type of antibiotics, their concentration and incubation time significantly
220 affected the food uptake in both species. Further, post-hoc (Tukey's post-hoc) test was applied
221 to test the differences between the used antibiotics and the control sample.

222

223 **3. Results**

224 Our first experimental setup with *Nonionella* sp. T1 showed that food (carbon and nitrogen)
225 uptake of this species was highly affected by the presence of antibiotics (p < 0.001), their
226 concentration (p < 0.001) and their interaction with each other (p < 0.001). Post hoc test of the
227 incorporated amount of carbon (pC) highlights the difference between the digested food in

228 each experiment. The control group metabolized significantly less carbon compared to the
229 foraminifera incubated with CAM, TET or MIX (p values provided in Table 1). However, no
230 difference (p = 0.188) in carbon uptake was observed between control group and foraminifera
231 incubated with AMP. In all experiments with *Nonionella* sp. T1 the mean values of the
232 incorporated carbon (pC) were higher if antibiotics were present in the culture medium (Fig.
233 2). The carbon uptake in the AMP spiked samples was not affected by the concentration (p =
234 0.640) of the antibiotics nor by time (p = 0.190). Also, the concentration of CAM did not appear
235 to influence the pC (p = 0.476), but here the amount of pC increased significantly (p=0.003)
236 with time. Similar to AMP, the TET concentration (p=0.351) and the incubation (p = 0.183) time
237 was not affecting the carbon uptake in this treatment. If all antibiotics were present in the
238 culture medium (MIX), the concentration of the antibiotics significantly (p < 0.001) decreased
239 pC and also significantly (p < 0.001) more carbon was incorporated with time.

240 The nitrogen uptake (pN) for *Nonionella* sp. T1 showed a different pattern. No significant
241 difference in pN was observed between the control group and AMP (p = 0.717) or TET (p =
242 0.501) group, but the presence of CAM (p = 0.011) or MIX (p = 0.002) significantly increased
243 pN in this species (Table 1). Between three and seven days no significant difference (p = 0.701)
244 was observed in pN of the control group. The concentration of AMP in the culture medium
245 appeared to play a significant role (p = 0.023), as did the time of incubation (p = 0.021). At a
246 low level (AMP_c1) this antibiotic did not influence pN during the incubation (p = 0.437), but
247 at c2 a significant increase (p = 0.046) of pN was noticed during the incubation (Fig. 2). At
248 presence of CAM in the culture medium with *Nonionella* sp. T1 an opposite trend was
249 observed. Here the lower concentration c1 led to an increase of pN with time (p = 0.008) and
250 at c2 no significant difference (p = 0.454) was observed between three and seven days of
251 incubation (Fig. 2). Finally, for TET, its low concentration (c1) decreased the pN with time (p =
252 0.006), whilst at TET c2 no significant influence (p = 0.134) was observed in pN between day
253 three and seven. In both c1 and c2 concentrations the presence of all three antibiotics together
254 (MIX) led to an increase of pN with time (c1: p < 0.001; c2: p = 0.11) (Fig. 2).

255 To investigate the influence of antibiotics on the overall metabolism of foraminifera, the ratio
256 of pC:pN was used (Fig. 3). This ratio must always be seen in comparison to the control sample.
257 Generally, the higher the slope value, the better is foraminiferal fitness during the experiment,
258 since a low value means an increase in pN, which is equivalent to the production of stress
259 proteins (Lintner et al., 2025). All control samples have the lowest slope (y = 2.8342x) in all
260 treatments (Fig. 3), which indicates that the presence of antibiotics contributes significantly to
261 changes in the metabolism of the foraminifera. In the AMP, CAM and MIX experiments the
262 slope of c2 is lower than c1 suggesting higher stress for *Nonionella* sp. T1 caused by higher
263 level of antibiotics (Fig. 3a, b and d). Only for the TET experiments the slope of c1 is lower than
264 c2, which correlates with the observation that at c1 pC as well as pN decreases in contrast to
265 c2, where both pC and pN increase (Fig. 3d). This highlights, that *Nonionella* sp. T1 incubated
266 with TET likely perform better at its higher concentrations, whereas all other antibiotics harm
267 this species at elevated concentrations.

268

269 Table 1: Post hoc test of carbon (yellow) and nitrogen (green) uptake in *Nonionella* sp. T1 and *H. depressa*.
270 Significant values are shown in bold. Control indicates foraminifera incubated without any antibiotics. The

271 abbreviations indicate the antibiotics present during incubation: AMP – Ampicillin; CAM – Chloramphenicol, TET
 272 – Tetracycline, MIX – mixture of all three used antibiotics (AMP, CAM and TET).

<i>Nonionella</i> T1	Control	AMP	CAM	TET	MIX		<i>H. depressa</i>	Control	AMP	CAM	TET	MIX
Control		0.188	<0.001	0.008	<0.001		Control		0.968	0.001	<0.001	<0.001
AMP	0.717		0.006	0.512	<0.001		AMP	0.380		0.001	<0.001	<0.001
CAM	0.011	0.088		0.259	0.851		CAM	0.957	0.030		<0.001	0.001
TET	0.501	0.994	0.205		0.029		TET	0.214	<0.001	0.432		0.988
MIX	0.002	0.019	0.968	0.053			MIX	0.580	0.002	0.885	0.935	

273

274

275 Figure 2: Carbon (pC, left) and nitrogen (pN, right) uptake from *Nonionella* sp. T1 after three (3d)
 276 days of incubation. The abbreviations indicate the control (C) sample or the antibiotics added during incubation:
 277 AMP – Ampicillin; CAM – Chloramphenicol, TET – Tetracycline, MIX – mixture of all three used antibiotics (AMP,
 278 CAM and TET). 1 is the manufacturer's recommended concentration to remove bacterial activity in culture
 279 medium, 2 corresponds to ten times the concentration of 1.

280

281

282 Figure 3: pC:pN ratios from *Nonionella sp. T1*. The abbreviations indicate the antibiotics added during incubation:
 283 AMP – Ampicillin; CAM – Chloramphenicol, TET – Tetracycline, MIX – mixture of all three used antibiotics (AMP,
 284 CAM and TET). C1 is the manufacturer's recommended concentration to remove bacterial activity in culture
 285 medium, c2 corresponds to ten times the concentration of c1.

286

287 For our second experimental setup with *Heterostegina depressa*, the incorporated amount of
 288 carbon (IC) in this species significantly depends on the type of antibiotics ($p < 0.001$), exposure
 289 time ($p < 0.001$) and also interaction between different antibiotics ($p < 0.001$). Carbon uptake
 290 in the control group was similar to *H. depressa* incubated with AMP ($p = 0.968$) but significantly
 291 differed ($p < 0.001$) from all other treatments (CAM, TET and MIX) (Table 1). The concentration
 292 of AMP did not affect ($p = 0.056$) IC, but for both concentrations c1 and c2 a significant increase
 293 of IC with time was observed (c1: $p = 0.006$; c2: $p = 0.036$). However, a higher concentration of
 294 CAM significantly ($p = 0.008$) reduced the carbon uptake by *H. depressa*. At the higher CAM
 295 concentration (c2) no time exposure effect ($p = 0.515$) was observed and just a trend ($p =$
 296 0.086) for increasing carbon uptake exists for c1 (Fig. 4). Tetracycline drastically reduced the
 297 activity of the foraminifera and its concentration appeared to play a significant ($p < 0.001$) role.
 298 At the same time, between three and seven days of incubation for both TET concentrations
 299 (c1: $p = 0.769$; c2: $p = 0.662$) no significant difference was observed. At c2 the uptake was close
 300 to zero, indicating a total lack of activity (likely suggesting mortality) of *H. depressa* individuals
 301 even at the shortest time of incubation with TET. The same pattern was found for *H. depressa*
 302 incubated with MIX of all antibiotics. The higher concentration significantly ($p < 0.001$) reduced
 303 foraminiferal activity, and the low concentration (c1) showed no significant ($p = 0.543$) effect
 304 of time exposure. However, a significant ($p = 0.010$) difference shown as reduction with time
 305 was calculated for c2, which could be explained by the fact that after 3 days there were still
 306 very low values of IC in *H. depressa* and after 7 days an absolute zero IC value was measured
 307 (Fig. 4). At this point it must also be mentioned that the culture medium, which included TET
 308 had changed colour from slight yellow to dark red over time. This phenomenon was not

309 observed with TET-treatment for *Nonionella* sp. T1 because of their incubation in dark
 310 conditions. However, the cultivation of *H. depressa* occurred under light exposure, causing TET
 311 to decompose, which likely created toxic decomposition products.

312 The amount of nitrogen (IN) incorporated by *H. depressa* was also highly affected ($p < 0.001$)
 313 by the presence of antibiotics, whilst not by the incubation time ($p = 0.293$) but rather by their
 314 interaction ($p = 0.045$) (Fig. 4). While the concentration of AMP appeared to be of less
 315 importance ($p = 0.1486$) in nitrogen processing of *H. depressa*, all other setups with a higher
 316 level of antibiotics reduced the activity of foraminifera significantly (CAM: $p = 0.039$; TET: $p <$
 317 0.001 ; MIX: $p < 0.001$) (Table 1). The IC:IN ratio was also calculated for *H. depressa* (Fig. 5).
 318 However, the values are subject to a significantly higher spread, which makes them hard to
 319 interpret. For *Nonionella* sp. T1, the values after three and seven days for the pC:pN are on the
 320 same trendline, only shifted towards higher values. In *H. depressa*, the three- and seven-day
 321 values do not plot together, which leads to a decrease in the regression and increased the
 322 scatter of data. Antibiotics with a presumably weaker influence, such as AMP or CAM, do not
 323 allow herein for any clear statements about fitness of *H. depressa*. However, antibiotics with a
 324 clearly negative effect such as TET or MIX also show a shift in the trend line towards a smaller
 325 slope, indicating stressful conditions for this species (Fig. 5).

326
 327 Figure 4: Carbon (IC, left) and nitrogen (IN, right) uptake from *H. depressa* after three (3d) and seven (7d) days of
 328 incubation. The abbreviation C indicate the control sample. Abbreviations for antibiotics added during incubation:
 329 AMP – Ampicillin; CAM – Chloramphenicol, TET – Tetracycline, MIX – mixture of all three used antibiotics (AMP,
 330 CAM and TET). 1 is the manufacturer's recommended concentration to remove bacterial activity in culture
 331 medium, 2 corresponds to ten times the concentration of 1.

332
 A

B

333

334 Figure 5: IC:IN ratios for *H. depressa*. The abbreviations indicate the antibiotics added during incubation: , IC –
 335 incorporated carbon; IN – incorporated nitrogen; AMP – Ampicillin; CAM – Chloramphenicol, TET – Tetracycline,
 336 MIX – mixture of all three used antibiotics (AMP, CAM and TET). C1 is the manufacturer's recommended
 337 concentration to remove bacterial activity in culture medium, c2 corresponds to ten times the concentration of
 338 c1.

339

340 4. Discussion

341 4.1. The response of foraminifera to antibiotics

342 Based on our results antibiotic-spiked culture medium appears to cause significant changes in
 343 the metabolism of both small and large benthic foraminifera, represented by changes in C:N
 344 ratios of the species *Nonionella* sp. T1 and *Heterostegina depressa*, respectively. How affected
 345 the foraminifera are depends on both the type and concentration of the used antibiotics. The
 346 addition of AMP appears to have the weakest impact on both studied species, but at this point
 347 it is also questionable whether AMP ever had any influence on the foraminifera. The effective
 348 time (time of action before it will decompose) of AMP is around 8 hours (Zhang and Trissel,
 349 2002) and it is unstable at high pH values (Mitchell et al., 2014), typical for seawater. Hence,
 350 we can assume that the influence of AMP on foraminifera was likely there only within the first
 351 few hours of incubation. This is consistent, with the low AMP treatment (c1) showing the
 352 metabolism of the foraminifera, similar to that of the control group. The high concentration
 353 did not have a significant effect on the metabolism of *Nonionella* sp. T1, but a slight decrease
 354 was noticeable in *H. depressa*. Since c2 was ten times higher in concentration than c1, it can
 355 be assumed, that it took longer until there was hardly any active AMP in the culture water. At
 356 the same time *H. depressa* was incubated at higher temperatures, which would cause faster
 357 decay of AMP. It is reasonable to believe that *Nonionella* sp. T1 would be more affected by the
 358 higher AMP concentration since its incubation was at lower temperature, but this was not the

359 case. Hence, our results suggest that the effect of ampicillin on the metabolism of foraminifera
360 is highly species dependent.

361 Our study further shows that presence of CAM in the culture water did not have a negative
362 effect on *Nonionella* sp. T1, whereas CAM greatly reduced the metabolism of *H. depressa*. The
363 hydrolysis of CAM is only significant at high pH values (<9) and this antibiotic is also stable at
364 the temperature range here tested (Shaw, 1975). Based on these assumptions, it can be
365 assumed that both foraminifera interacted with CAM throughout the entire incubation period.
366 Similar to the experiment with AMP, our results once again confirmed that *H. depressa* is more
367 sensitive to the presence of antibiotics and that the reaction to CAM is species-specific as well.

368 Our results also highlight the strongest difference in metabolism observed for the two studied
369 foraminiferal species in experimental setups with TET and MIX. However, this is not necessarily
370 related to the response of the foraminifera to the antibiotics but can be explained by
371 differences in experimental set ups. Since TET (note: also present in MIX treatment) is strongly
372 affected by photodegradation, it is likely that light exposure in *H. depressa* experiments caused
373 formation of secondary products, like reactive oxygen species (ROS), which likely negatively
374 affected the foraminifera (Oluwole and Olatunji, 2022). On the other hand, there is much less
375 probability for formation of these secondary products in the culture of *Nonionella* sp. T1
376 because of incubations in the dark. Whilst there was also no negative effect on the metabolism
377 of *Nonionella* sp. T1, we observed a complete deactivation or mortality in *H. depressa*. This
378 suggests that the secondary products resulting from TET photodegradation can be more toxic
379 to foraminifera than the antibiotic itself.

380 Finally, we would like to compare our results with previous studies. Based on past data, most
381 studies used streptomycin to investigate its effects on foraminifera. In three (Nigram et al.,
382 1996; Arnold 1966; Pierce 1965) of four studies using streptomycin (Pierce, 1965 used
383 dihydrostreptomycin), an increase in foraminifera growth was observed when the antibiotic
384 was present in the culture medium. A positive effect on foraminiferal growth was also
385 observed as soon as CAM was present in the culture medium (Arnold, 1966; Pierce, 1965). We
386 can only partially confirm this result with our data, since CAM has a potential positive effect
387 on the metabolism of *Nonionella* sp. T1, but a clearly negative influence on *H. depressa*.
388 Further Pierce (1965) noticed a positive effect of tetracycline (0.04%) on growth of
389 foraminifera, but nothing was mentioned about the light conditions during the experiment. In
390 our experiments we used 100 µg/ml and 1000 µg/ml TET which is equal to 0.01% and 0.1%
391 and is therefore comparable with the concentrations used by Pierce (1965). However,
392 foraminifera react similar to TET and to CAM. Again *Nonionella* sp. T1 was not negatively
393 affected by the antibiotics but the metabolisms of *H. depressa* failed completely, which was
394 probably caused by the photodegradation of TET as discussed earlier. As conclusion, it should
395 be mentioned once again that the effect of antibiotics on foraminifera is very species-
396 dependent and that the foraminifera used in the laboratory must first be tested for their
397 response to antibiotics before they can be cultivated with them.

398

399 4.2. Environmental risk of antibiotics

400 Apart from the new knowledge provided by this study for foraminifera culture experiments,
401 how can these results be put into an ecological context as mentioned above? Ampicillin is not
402 stable in media with high pH, which is typical for seawater. Accordingly, it is likely that AMP
403 does not pose a direct threat to marine organisms, except in regions where there is a
404 continuously high discharge of this antibiotic into coastal waters. The situation is similar with
405 TET, which instead of being influenced by the pH, degrades when exposed to light. However,
406 due to the enormous present consumption of TET (e.g. >2500 T per year in the European
407 Union) and the low rate of its metabolism in the organisms (up to 75% will be excreted),
408 tetracycline potentially poses a serious problem in the environment (Daghrir and Drogui, 2013;
409 Xu et al., 2021). It was shown that freshwater algae exhibit toxic effects at TET concentrations
410 > 5 mg/L and at 30 mg/L they show a 94% growth inhibition (Xu et al., 2019; Amangelsin et al.,
411 2023). In our experiments, at TET c1 treatment, despite having significantly higher
412 concentrations (100 mg/L), we did not observe any negative effect on *Nonionella* sp. T1, which
413 suggests that some foraminiferal species may be more tolerant to TET than other organisms
414 such as algae. Of all the antibiotics tested, CAM probably has the highest potential to have a
415 negative effect on organisms in the marine environment. In seawater samples from the Herglas
416 Sea in Tunisia concentrations of 15.6 µg/L of CAM were recorded (Tahrani et al., 2016). But
417 apart from these hotspots, common CAM concentrations in seawater are between 0.02 and
418 0.15 µg/L (Nguyen et al., 2022). Those concentrations observed in field by previous studies are
419 now a factor of 1000 lower than those we used in our experiments. However, since the
420 metabolism of our tested foraminifera was only slightly reduced in the presence of CAM (Figs
421 2, 4) and this concentration was artificially high, we cannot assume that in nature there is a
422 negative CAM influence on foraminifera from the currently measured antibiotic
423 concentrations. Additionally, our experiments only provide information about short-term
424 effects on foraminifera caused by antibiotics. Future studies should address whether long-term
425 antibiotic exposure? in lower concentrations is more harmful to foraminifera, than exposures
426 tested herein, to further investigate resilience of these microeukaryotic organisms.

427

428 5. Conclusions

429 We tested the influence of three antibiotics, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and tetracycline, and
430 their mixture on the metabolism of two foraminiferal species. Our results show that both
431 species are affected by the presence of antibiotics, but the effects of antibiotics are species
432 specific. In general, *Heterostegina depressa* responds more sensitively to the presence of
433 antibiotics in culture water than *Nonionella* sp. T1, the latter seems to even benefit from the
434 presence of antibiotics. Treatment with ampicillin showed the least negative influence
435 probably because of a quick ampicillin hydrolyse due to its instability at high pH typical of
436 seawater and therefore it is likely that ampicillin only interacted with the foraminifera for a
437 few hours. On the other hand, chloramphenicol showed a significant reduction in the
438 metabolism of the foraminifera (especially in *H. depressa*) indicated by isotopic uptake of
439 carbon and nitrogen. However, the strongest influence in our study was observed for
440 treatments with tetracycline and mixture of all three antibiotics. Tetracycline reduced the
441 activity of *H. depressa* to zero within just three days (possibly faster), which is likely caused by
442 its toxic decay products, which arise during incubation with light. In contrast, a negative effect

443 of tetracycline on *Nonionella* sp. T1 when incubated in the dark conditions is hardly noticeable.
444 It is important to note, that we have chosen artificially high concentrations of antibiotics in our
445 study to improve future laboratory experiments. To the best of our knowledge, comparably
446 high concentrations in nature are currently not available, which makes it reasonable to believe
447 that the current levels of antibiotics in marine habitats likely do not have a negative impact on
448 foraminifera. However, there is a range of different antibiotics and a high diversity of species,
449 of which we have only tested a few in this study. Hence, future studies must be carried out
450 including several antibiotic types and testing other species to find out which antibiotics have
451 a negative effect on foraminifera and which antibiotics are best to apply to constrain culture
452 experiments.

453

454 Author contribution

455 ML designed and conducted the experiments, analysed the data, and wrote the manuscript.
456 IPA collected sediment in the Fjord and, together with ML, wrote the first draft of the
457 manuscript. WW organized the isotope measurements. PH provided foraminifera from her
458 laboratory. JG assisted with incubation at the ING PAN. JT helped with the study design. All
459 authors read the manuscript carefully.

460

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